

Condition Based Maintenance of Military Ground Vehicles

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Abstract—The performance of military ground vehicle systems quickly degrades due to high operation tempo and extreme environments while performing in-theater service. Current maintenance methods associated with this degradation are not sufficiently optimized for cost and performance. To address this issue, the United States Army is implementing a policy of Condition Based Maintenance (CBM) and being supported by the Army Materiel System Analysis Activity (AMSAA). CBM is a plan of maintenance for a system based upon the actual condition of the system as enabled by the application of usage, diagnostic and prognostic processes executed on a Health and Usage Monitoring System (HUMS).

AMSAA has developed and is implementing a CBM system for ground vehicles. This development process has included the development of a robust military-grade HUMS in conjunction with the Aberdeen Test Center and the development of data collection, reduction, analysis, and reporting processes. A key requirement underlying these processes is a thorough understanding of both the ways in which system condition is degenerated and the ability of the HUMS to detect, identify, and communicate all conditions that requires maintenance in a timely manner. AMSAA and the US Army Aberdeen Test Center (ATC) have jointly initiated testing and applications as the critical means of filling this requirement.^{1 2}

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1. INTRODUCTION

Condition based maintenance (CBM) is a plan of maintenance for a system based upon the actual condition of the system as enabled by the application of usage, diagnostic and prognostic processes executed on a Health and Usage Monitoring System (HUMS). Usage refers to the manner in which the system is employed and gives indications of how and why things are broken or breaking. Usage characteristics include hours running, miles driven, time at idle and fuel consumed among many others collected from on board vehicle sensors. Diagnostics is based on the symptoms or indicators of problems and uses methods to find what is broken and/or breaking in a system. The ultimate goal of HUMS is to leverage the knowledge base gained with usage and diagnostics in developing prognostic algorithms that will enable the prediction of system failures and, therefore, required system maintenance actions before failures occur. This will ultimately improve efficiency, reduce logistics costs, and improve driver and crew safety.

In order to foster the development of prognostic algorithms in support of condition based maintenance; AMSAA in conjunction with Aberdeen Test Center (ATC) has also initiated Seeded Fault Testing on ground vehicles. This test introduced, or seeded, known controlled faults into the vehicle in order to replicate common field failures. Common faults included lowering coolant levels, restricting air flow across radiator, lowering of transmission oil levels and lowering of engine oil levels. Data from the vehicle system was then collected and analyzed to observe how the system reacts.

2. AMSAA’S STRATEGY

AMSAA follows a four phase strategy for implementation of CBM. These phases are similar to the engineering design process. In phase one, AMSAA identified appropriate hardware and software for an Engineering Development HUMS (EDHUMS) and completed initial in-theater installations of data acquisition systems at Aberdeen Proving Ground (APG). In order to be used in theater on Tactical Wheeled Vehicles (TWV’s) the data acquisition system needs to meet certain specifications. The specifications the system must meet are:

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² IEEEAC paper #1736, Version 4, Updated December 11, 2008

- Dust tight and water tight connections
- Small overall size
- Use robust military grade connectors
- Accept 12V and 24 V power inputs
- provide method for remote switching of the unit (on/off)
- supports vehicle bus, GPS, displacement, strain, acceleration, and temperature gauges
- operates in maximum outside ambient temperature of 120°F (49°C) with a solar radiation load up to 1120 W/m²
- meets conducted emissions and susceptibility requirements of MIL-STD-461
- survives typical vibration levels of various TWV's

AMSAA began evaluating the capabilities of many commercial and military systems and selected an industrial-grade commercial off-the shelf product from nCode called the eDAQ-Lite shown in Figure 1. This system possesses the functionality, flexibility and ease of use necessary to support the development of CBM and prognostics algorithms in process.

Figure 1 – Image of eDAQ - lite

Phase two in AMSAA’s strategy consisted of developing a robust military-grade EDHUMS, designing a data analysis process, testing EDHUMS in the Continental United States (CONUS) training environment, and beginning to field EDHUMS in operational units outside of the CONUS including the Central Command’s area of responsibility.

While the eDAQ-lite off the shelf met some of the criteria specified for TWV’s; there were still some limitations. These included that the eDAQ-lite design was designed for industrial use (operating temperature: -10 °C to 65 °C and operating voltage: 10-18V), built with industrial-grade connectors instead of military grade, possessed no additional electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding / no tests for EMI, no internal relay for switching unit on/off, no internal motion sensors, and the vehicle engine bus interface module existed external to the unit. To correct these

problems AMSAA had to modify the eDAQ-lite in order to ensure the survivability of it in the field, enhance the functionality, and control the EMI to and from communications gear.

First, a military grade superstructure was designed in Pro/Engineer (a 3D solid-modeling package) to house the eDAQ-lite data acquisition system, shown in Figure 2, along with other essential support equipment and cables.

Figure 2 - Original 3D Solid-Model of eDAQ-lite within Superstructure (US ARMY eDAQ TWV Package)

Support equipment included EMI filters and fuses on the power lines, a DC/DC converter, a solid-state relay to switch the eDAQ-lite on and off, a six degree of freedom motion pack to provide three angular rates and acceleration information along three orthogonal directions, and a vehicle bus interface module to provide communications between the vehicle bus and the eDAQ-lite.

Two thermal tests were performed to characterize the thermal behavior of the US ARMY eDAQ TWV system under desert operating conditions (as specified in AR 70-38). The first test was a steady-state, natural convection test designed to determine the maximum operating temperature of the eDAQ system. The second test was a solar-loading test designed to validate the operation of the eDAQ system when exposed to high solar radiation in conjunction with high outside ambient temperatures. A conduction-based cooling scheme was selected for the interior components (including the eDAQ-lite) and a natural-convection-based cooling scheme was selected for the exterior. Thermally conductive grease/RTV/gasket was used on all wall interfaces. Figure 3 and 4 show the built ARMY eDAQ TWV Package.

Figure 3 - Installed ARMY eDAQ TWV Package

Figure 4 - ARMY eDAQ TWV Package with lid removed

Phase three of AMSAA's strategy was identifying a small, inexpensive Focused HUMS (FHUMS). This would be a HUMS device identified as a commercial system that met most of the requirements identified for the EDHUMS including the requirement of being capable to support all the sensors and data recording devices of the EDHUMS. It also had to meet the additional requirements of being smaller and more cost efficient. The system needed to be small enough in order to fit in more discrete locations than could previously be occupied by the EDHUMS. This was a must as to not interfere with any standard operating procedures of the vehicle and to make it totally autonomous to the operator. It also allows for easier installation and shorter installation times. AMSAA was successful in identifying a company that manufactured vehicle monitoring units (VMU) for this purpose and was willing to work with AMSAA to develop flexible customization of their hardware and software to meet AMSAA's requirements.

AMSAA took the most versatile version of the VMU and co-developed with the manufacturer the ability to meet specific requirements for a FHUMS. Once the first version of the FHUMS was ready AMSAA began running tests at Aberdeen Proving Ground and Yuma Proving ground to

prove the ability of the FHUMS to produce accurate reports and data. Two tests were run with military vehicles having an EDHUMS and a FHUMS recording data simultaneously. The goal of the tests was to determine if the FHUMS system could replicate the algorithms and reports on the FHUMS that were produced post processed on the EDHUMS. The results of previous tests and field data using the EDHUMS were analyzed and used to create the format for the data to be produced in the summary reports created by the FHUMS. The tests confirmed that the FHUMS could produce ready to go reports that users, maintainers, commanders, engineers, supply chain personnel, and project managers could refer to in their decision making processes. The next step was to customize the FHUMS for AMSAA's requirements, by formatting the processed data, improving the FHUMS harness system, adding internal calculation ability for performing algorithms and improving the software interface, as well as adding additional external sensor capability. The second version of VMU was a smaller FHUMS system that the company offers but customized for AMSAA's requirements including accepting new sensors and the J1708 interface. This version included many of the software upgrades including new data formats and hardware changes. It was also used to initially field the FHUMS on a smaller level at many locations. The third version included a few upgrades and is the current version being deployed and planned to deploy over the next year. Figure 4a shows an installed FHUMS. The planned changes for the FHUMS includes adding firmware upgrades to include new algorithms and adding in additional health sensors that work with the FHUMS such as temperature and current monitors. These added sensors and the potential of being able to add more sensors add to the flexibility of AMSAA being able to meet the present and future concerns of the army fleet management.

Figure 4a - Army FHUMS

AMSAA's fourth and final phase is integrating these smaller FHUMS into all military vehicles at the point of manufacturing or, in the case of older vehicles, RESET. RESET is when all vehicles and equipment get a complete teardown, overhaul and necessary upgrades which it is hoped that one day include FHUMS. These boxes will collect data on fleets as well as have on-board algorithms implemented in order to warn the operators of impending failures as well as assist the maintainers and command.

3. DATA REPORTING

Many vehicles at Aberdeen Proving Ground have been fully instrumented with EDHUMS and data is being captured from over 80 analog channels, multiple SAE J-1708/J-1939 bus channels, and GPS sensors. These vehicles have run over all APG test courses multiple times which has provided detailed data for prognostic algorithm development. These are algorithms that AMSAA creates from the data to predict impending failures before they happen in order to warn the operator and the maintainers so proper evasive action can be taken. Aberdeen Test Center (ATC) and AMSAA have also measured and analyzed data from 20 wheeled vehicles of 3 different types in Iraq for over a year. This has provided a significant amount of usage data and operating parameters that have been extremely useful for optimizing testing. Also, the data is being aligned with maintenance records to identify which maintenance actions and failures occur most in the field. This information can then be used to develop specific prognostics algorithms for those actions that would provide value in theater.

EDHUMS testing has been ongoing since June 2006. AMSAA has instrumented and collected data from TWV's at the National Training Center in Ft. Irwin, California and Ft. Stewart, Georgia. Ten EDHUMS systems were installed in Kuwait/Iraq in 2007 and six systems were installed in Afghanistan. In addition, six systems were installed during the Heavy Brigade Combat Team CBM+ COBRA demonstration in April 2007.

AMSAA is recording a large variety of time-history data on all of the instrumented vehicles and is able to summarize usage items like time-in-gear, which is the amount of time that the vehicle spends in each of its transmission gears and time-at-speed, which is a speed distribution profile. AMSAA is also able to perform multi-parameter analyses to investigate fuel and driveline efficiencies.

Figure 5 - Latitude and longitude plot of speed (green) and Terrain-Induced Vibration

One of the most promising analytical processes AMSAA is developing is the real-time onboard identification, classification, and mapping of terrain types as shown in Figure 5. This work has led to a usable initial terrain identification and classification algorithm that has been implemented onboard all vehicles currently instrumented by AMSAA in Kuwait, Iraq, Afghanistan, Korea, and the United States. While current implementation is somewhat rudimentary - only 3 broad-spectrum short-wavelength surface roughness classifications - work is underway to incorporate long-wavelength classifications (hills, mountains, etc) as well as a refinement to the shorter-wavelength terrains.

Presently, the algorithm distinguishes 3 severities of surface roughness - primary road, secondary road, and off-road - using a root-mean-square calculation of data from unsprung mass accelerometers low-pass filtered at 30 Hz as a function of mean vehicle speed over 20-second periods. Given that the suspension of the vehicle responds to short-wavelength terrain components (bumps, washboarding, etc) in the form of high accelerations, the accelerometer is an appropriate sensor for these shorter-wavelengths. On the other hand, the suspension does not respond to long wavelength components such as hills in any measurable amount. The overall vehicle orientation - the pitch and roll angles, however, does. The appropriate sensor for this measurement is a gyroscope.

Most AMSAA instrumentation packages incorporate a low-cost "motion pack" (triaxial gyro and triaxial accelerometer) sensor that more accurately responds to the long wavelength, hilly components of the terrain. Development work is underway to incorporate these measurements into an integrated full-spectrum - very long to very short wavelength - terrain identification algorithm. These concepts are illustrated in Figure 6 below.

Figure 6 - PSD Plots of Wavelength Contributions to Terrain Classifications and Sensor Sensitivity

One of the current products that AMSAA can quickly output in the field from the data collected is our Vehicle Usage Summary Report. It is a two-page report that summarizes some of the important parameters of vehicle usage.

Included in the report is the vehicle's ID, the date and time the data were taken, the total amount of fuel that was consumed, the amount of fuel consumed while the vehicle was at idle, the percentage of time the vehicle was at idle, significant damage/safety events (the count of hard brake and hard turn maneuvers), the amount of time spent in primary, secondary, and off-road terrain, and a map of the vehicle's route. Also distribution profiles of speed, engine coolant temperature, engine and transmission oil temperatures, engine speed, and transmission gearing are shown. Figure 6 shown below is an example of a Vehicle Usage Summary Report.

Figure 6 - Vehicle Usage Summary report

4. SEEDED FAULT TESTING & ALGORITHM DEVELOPMENT

AMSAA's seeded fault testing was created in order to develop prognostic algorithms for CBM's EDHUMS box as well as the VMU FHUMS. During this test AMSAA introduced known controlled faults into the vehicle in order

to replicate common field failures. Common faults included lowering coolant levels, restricting air flow across radiator, lowering of transmission oil levels and lowering of engine oil levels. It is predicted that this will cause the vehicle cooling system to fail or overheat which is a major cause of in theater failures. Testing was conducted at Aberdeen Proving Ground, Maryland and then at Yuma Proving Ground, Arizona. Three courses from each Proving Ground were selected to encompass a full range of terrain types and conditions. The extremely high temperatures during the June/July desert testing at Yuma mimic closely that of Iraq. It is also predicted that the outside air temperature has a large effect on the cooling system and performance of vehicles which is why Yuma Proving Ground was selected in the test plan.

This test will provide many useful findings. First, the results will be used in order to advance the development of CBM and predictive vehicle algorithms coordinated with diagnostics and prognostics methods. Second, there has not been, to AMSAA's knowledge, any experiment detailing the vehicle's performance under extreme and unconventional conditions. These conditions include running the vehicle over rough terrain in excessive heat while the vehicle overheats or is pushed close to failure. Third, it shows indisputable evidence of whether or not our EDHUMS is capable of showing faults in the data as well as having the potential to deliver the required algorithms.

The vehicle was instrumented with J1939 data bus recording capability and GPS to replicate the instrumentation AMSAA uses in the field. Twelve thermocouples were also instrumented on the vehicle in specific locations as a validation of the temperatures being recorded from the J1708 data bus.

For each of the three fluid level reduction tests, fluid was removed in increments relative to the total fluid capacity in order to produce a large enough sample size as well as a linear comparison curve in the data. Each level of fluid in the vehicle represented one run around the course and the test was done until the vehicle recorded failure of any kind including overheating. During the radiator blockage test the same ideas were put into place and runs were conducted as a percentage blocked of the total area. The data was then recorded and analyzed.

Preliminary results show that AMSAA's EDHUMS data can in fact show differences between runs of failure and non failure for the faults tested. Engine coolant reduction and radiator blockage showed elevated coolant temperatures as expected as well as elevated oil temperatures and intake air temperatures. The difference in data also shows that there is a distinguishing factor between overheating by coolant loss and by radiator blockage seen in the figures below.

Figure 7 - Coolant temperature and rate of change for vehicle overheating caused by radiator blockage

Figure 8 – Coolant temperature and rate of change for vehicle overheating caused by coolant loss

Figure 8 shows a coolant loss failure and the figure 7 shows overheating by radiator blockage. The blue lines represent the temperature of the actual coolant and the red line shows the rate of change of the coolant temperature. This was calculated by differentiating the coolant temperature, it is not a data stream that comes directly off the vehicles J1939 electronic control module. From the data both graphs show a rise in coolant temperature to a critical level; however, their nature is much different. The coolant loss chart shows a maximum rate of change to be +3 degrees and -2 degrees. However the radiator blockage chart shows only a maximum rate of change as +/- 1 degree. AMSAA currently developed an algorithm that can distinguish between these two faults and will soon be in the process of testing and validating this algorithm. AMSAA also is in the final stages of developing an oil loss algorithm. These algorithms have the potential to predict vehicle failure and warn the operator of impending failures possibly 10 to 15 minutes before they

occur, allowing the operator sufficient time to get to safety. Future work in seeded fault testing is necessary and will be conducted by AMSAA. This involves testing many different faults under in-theater conditions as well as verifying any algorithms created. It is AMSAA's overall goal to use seeded fault testing in conjunction with CBM to have the ability to use algorithms developed by seeded fault implanted in-theater and save cost, time and increase the efficiency of vehicle maintenance and safety.

5. CONCLUSION

AMSAA has developed and is implementing a condition based maintenance system for military ground vehicles in order to plan maintenance based upon the actual condition of the system as enabled by the application of usage, diagnostic and prognostic processes executed on a Health and Usage Monitoring System (HUMS). A data acquisition system was ruggedized and modified to meet military standards and usage requirements in order to fill the need of a high operation tempo and extreme environments the vehicles endure. Testing was done to validate and verify algorithms developed and created by seeded fault testing along with in theater usage data. It is AMSAA hope that a focused HUMS will be used on all military vehicles in the future in order to provide operators, maintainers, suppliers and commanders with necessary data to make good fleet management decisions ultimately saving time and money while increasing maintenance efficiency and operator safety.

REFERENCES

[1] Aerospace Conference Web site <http://www.aeroconf.org/>

BIOGRAPHY

Eric Rabeno is a Mechanical Engineer and a member of the Condition Based Maintenance Team at The US Army Materiel Systems Analysis Activity located on Aberdeen Proving Ground, Maryland. He has a Bachelor of Science degree in Mechanical Engineering with a Minor in Mathematics from the University of Delaware. He is also in the process of obtaining a Master of Science degree in Biomedical Engineering from Johns Hopkins University.

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